

Rehabilitation In a Perspective of a Combined Ecosystem of the “Ancient and Modern Indian Techniques” in The Field of Physiotherapy.

Proposed Multidisciplinary Rehabilitation Approach

¹Dr. Mumux Mirani,

¹Assistant Professor,

¹S. S. Agrawal Institute of Physiotherapy and Medical Care Education affiliated to Veer Narmad South Gujarat University (VNSGU), Navsari, Gujarat, India, 396445.

Abstract : In a modern era of the physiotherapy field is blooming with the various rehabilitation approach as the new and innovative techniques are widely in a use by the Indian physiotherapist. As the rehabilitation methods are fairly based on treating patient and make them independent to do active daily living activities as well as sports activities to make them active physically, mentally, socially and spiritually also then the current physiotherapy approaches should be utilized with a combination of ancient Indian rehabilitation techniques for betterment in rehabilitation regarding the same. This combined clinical perspective is also referring to make a combined ecosystem to rehabilitate in a way of modern as well as ancient Indian way in the field of physiotherapy.

Key words - Ecosystem, Rehabilitation, Physiotherapy, Periodization.

I. INTRODUCTION

A very long-time physical culture is used as a prophylactic and therapeutic agent and/or way in various diseases. Even in ancient times was used for health promotion exercise, sauna (bath), massage, hydrotherapy, diet, and other means. In Indian older times, in bad joint mobility used by stretching, massage and water therapy. The development of Vedic literature was started in the time of Indus valley civilization (Hindu civilization). Vyayama or Exercise is an importance practice of ancient India as per the evidence of Harappa civilization.[1]

It is noted that, an ancient Indian surgeon Sushruta in his practice applies physical, breathing exercises as well as massage and hardening. Yogis have used at least 800 of breathing exercises, most of all- for holding one's breath, with the help of these exercises are prevented and treated disease. It highlighted the fact that Vyayama is for the sustained development of human being. Caraka Samhita emphasized on maintenance of positive health which include proper diet, sleep, rest, active habit, regular exercise etc. It also indicated the negative impact of excessive Vyayama (exercise) such as - exhaustion, consumption, thirst, bleeding from different parts of the body, dyspnea, cough, fever, vomiting etc. Caraka Samhita described about the Vyayama (exercise) practice as per the different seasons.[2]

Physiotherapy dates back in 250 A.D., when gold fish-electric fish was used for pain relief in gout and headache cases. In prehistoric era, Buddhists and Hindus recognized “pain as a sensation” but gave a greater importance to its emotional aspects. Non-invasive methods were used for pain relief. Rubbing, diet, massage, physical therapy, etc. Noted the “movement” is the best treatment of the body.

As, above mentioned, the ancient ways were stepping stones for the new age of the physiotherapy. Ecosystem which combines ancient and modern physiotherapy should lead the new innovation in rehabilitation.

This new ecosystem which includes Pranayama, yoga, asanas, meditation and a whole holistic approach with the modern evidence base physiotherapy tickle way to treat a patient. There should be an ecosystem that combines therapeutical approach to gain a beneficial effect in performance of a sports player or injured patient.

There are numerous ways in which we can explore the ecosystem and to combine the ancient and modern physical therapeutical approach.

For example, Sport specific rehabilitation will need the modern look of the periodization approach with a combination of ancient and modern views and thoughts which will help the player to rehabilitate him/her from his/her injuries and/or enhance his/her performance based on their requirement and approach for specific sports.

Inclusion of central concept of periodization method in which Alarm reaction, adaptation and exhaustion should be included with the periodic cycles which are mentioning macro-cycle meso-cycle and micro-cycle.

There should be sports specific activities and non-sport specific activities which will show the intensity and volume of the exercise and exercise period. Conventional periodization method can be used which includes 4 distinct periods.

For the non-sports specific manner, there should be high volume low intensity exercise methods and for the sport specific manner, that should be low volume and high intensity.

Making an ecosystem:

Ecosystem for combining ancient and modern physiotherapy approach, ancient way of rehabilitation Which includes psychological and physical approach for upbringing the positive physiological effects that should be included in micro-cycle of the periodization which is the new era of rehabilitation in the current scenario of sports physiotherapy.

Sports players often deal with the injuries which are drawing back them from being totally fit for their sports. They have injuries which affects them on their psychological and a physical approach for the games they are participating in it.

In recent times WHO suggested a new definition regarding physiotherapy and rehabilitation which includes the pointers showing physical psychological and spiritual well-being, so based on the modern era, spiritual as well as psychological aspect in upbringing the physical performance should be achieved in micro-cycle.[3]

As per modern era of sports physiotherapy, 3 stage responses to stress is observed any time the body experiences a novel, more intense stress than previously applied physiologically. General Adaptation Syndrome (GAS) given by Hans Selye in 1956, which overtime has become one of the foundational concepts from which periodization theories have developed. Alarm reaction, adaptation and exhaustion noted in these periodization ecosystems.[4]

As above mentioned, micro-cycle should be made with short term goals. This type of cycle should last for typically 1 week long, possibly up to 4 weeks, focuses on daily and weekly training variations. Then, it should lead towards meso-cycle which contains several weeks to months, depending on the goals of training and/or numbers of competitions within the period. These numbers of meso-cycles which are containing several different micro-cycles in approach of physical performances should show the macro-cycle which is entire training period typically 1 year in duration.

Antient ways: Dhyana (Meditation), Pranayama, Yoga, Asanas, Panchakarma, Vyayama, abhyangam and swasan kriya which shows the practice of breathing techniques Myofascial release with the rhino horn/ tusks of elephant, bodily well-being, and manual therapy, kriya- snaan (hydrotherapy, bathing related methods), akhara training, malkham training.

Modern ways: Meditation with breathing techniques, active-passive movements and exercises, stretching techniques, manual therapy techniques, electro-therapy, massage therapy, MFR by instruments and/or by manually hands on skills, hot-cold water therapy, hydrotherapy, cryotherapy sessions, cupping therapy, dry-needle methods, neuro-developmental therapy, neuro-muscular training, gym training.

Important Notes maintaining better combined ecosystem:

1. Ecosystem approach should be varied with different sports.
2. Cycle should be revised timely to break the monotonous working patterns.
3. Weekly player/Sports person's outcome measures should be taken (Sports anxiety scale, Performance/Fitness testing should be done).
4. Recording performance levels for comparing weekly and monthly progress with proper reporting and documentations should be done.
5. Weekly/Monthly psychological counselling should be done.

Proposed Combined Eco-System for Rehabilitation:**Micro-cycle for Combine ecosystem using antient and modern rehabilitation:**

Days	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday	Saturday	Sunday
Combined Approach	Warm Up activities, followed by FITT Protocol followed by Cool Down activities	Hypertrophy/ Resisted exercises followed by Hot-Cold Water Therapy (Snaan Kriya)	Warm up activities, followed by Sports specific training, Game training followed by Cool down activities, followed by Meditation, followed by Sports coping/ Psychological Evaluation	Active Rest And/or Yoga, Pranayama, Stretching Exercises	Functional training, Neuro-Muscular training, Surya-Namaskar, Yogasanas	Sports/ Game Strategy activities Training sessions for strategy activities Low Intensity Gym training	Total Rest And/or Active Rest (As per demand of sport)

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